

ADVERSE EFFECTS OF CHEMOTHERAPY ON KIDNEYS IN ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES.

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Relevance of the topic: Today, the chemotherapy method has been developed as an effective method for oncological diseases, and after the treatment, it has a negative effect on the kidneys in the body.

One of these effects is damage to the kidneys in the body, which means that when chemotherapy drugs enter the body, they can have a number of negative effects, including kidney function. Including toxic effects. In turn, chemotherapeutic drugs are sometimes associated with kidney tumors and poisoning. They can poison the glomeruli of the kidneys, that is, the main filtering mechanisms of the kidney, or damage other tissues of this organ. Also, hydration (dehydration) and electrolyte imbalance. Dehydration and electrolyte imbalance in the body during chemotherapy can make it difficult for the kidneys to function. This condition may be related to high-dose or long-term treatment with chemotherapeutic drugs and high temperature and similar conditions.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, patients living in the city of Urganch with oncological diseases and receiving chemotherapy were studied.

The results obtained: nephrotoxic effect was observed in the majority of oncological patients, i.e. toxic effect on kidney tissue, damage to the filtration system of the kidney, as well as glomeruli, dehydration of the body and violation of the electrolyte balance were observed.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the renal toxic effects of chemotherapy can vary widely, and these effects can be fatal in some cases. Therefore, taking nephrotoxic drugs under the supervision of a doctor, drinking plenty of water, choosing the right diet, regular monitoring of kidney function, and early diagnosis of problems related to the body are important measures to minimize the negative effects of chemotherapy.

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